

21ST CENTURY- COLLABORATIVE SKILLS: ASSESSING THE TEACHERS AND STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

Collaborative skills are behaviors that facilitate effective group collaboration and enable students to accomplish shared objectives. This study assessed 21st-century collaborative skills based on the perspectives of teachers and students. This study aimed to determine the significant relationship between teachers' and students' perspectives using 21st-century collaborative skills. ANOVA revealed a significant relationship between teachers' and students' perspectives on collaborative skills, as shown by the f-value of 0.780 and the p-value of 0.013. This study concluded that there is an association between teachers' and students' perspectives on 21st-century collaborative skills.

Keywords: 21st Century-Collaborative Skills, Teaching Practices, Students' Engagement, Socio-Demographic Profile.

INTRODUCTION

Globalization has opened doors, leading nations to co-exist and become interdependent (Bilbao et al., 2018). This interconnectedness encompasses individuals' knowledge, abilities, and principles. Modern curriculum designers believe that educational programs should be structured to help students grasp and comprehend fundamental academic concepts. Additionally, some scholars have suggested that "multiliteracy" can equip students to make well-informed choices, prepare them for global challenges, and enhance their prospects in the job market (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005).

Introducing students with diverse skills is crucial for cultivating a generation that can effectively navigate real-world situations. To achieve the authentic learning demanded in the 21st century, students effectively engage in the learning environment and develop 21st-century skills, such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration (Alismail & McGuire, 2015).

Moreover, collaboration encourages the enactment of learning mechanisms (such as induction, deduction, and associative learning) (Dillenbourg, 1999; Hunter, 2006). Collaborative skills refer to students working together to solve problems or answer questions, working effectively and respectfully in teams to accomplish a common goal, and assuming a shared responsibility

for completing a task (Ravitz, J. et al. (2014). Research has shown that collaborative activities enhance students' social abilities, such as resolving conflicts and offering assistance, as well as their academic self-perception (Ginsburg-Block, Rohrbeck, & Fantuzzo, 2006). While widely recognized as beneficial for classroom use and beyond, the concept of collaboration remains ambiguous (Brna, 1998). Students can improve their collaborative skills through team assignments and shared projects that require effective teamwork and communication (Rasmitadilaetal., 2021). Through collaborative activities, students learn to respect differences in opinions and work toward common goals (Nahar, 2022).

As Ravitz et al. (2014) noted, collaborative skills represent one of eight identified learning skills. These encompass students' aptitude for cooperative problem-solving and question-addressing, their ability to work respectfully and effectively in team settings to achieve collective goals, and their willingness to share accountability for task completion. Indeed, teachers must develop students into wholesome individuals to achieve the 21st-century skills of students. McCarten (2007) points out that most studies indicate that multiple exposures, both explicit and implicit, are necessary for retention.

With this, the study aimed to determine teachers' perceived teaching practices used in the classroom, students' perception of various teaching practices used by their teachers, and the significant relationship between teachers' and students' perceptions of teaching practices and student engagement. This study focused on assessing teachers' teaching practices and students' engagement in the teaching practices utilized by their teachers. The respondents of this study were 11 teachers and 145 students from Lubilan Integrated School and Mat-I National High School, Naawan Misamis Oriental, SY 2023-2024.

METHODOLOGY

This study sought to assess teachers' teaching practices and students' perceptions of the teaching practices utilized by teachers using 21st century-collaborative skills. This study used a descriptive, quantitative research design. To select the sample size of the respondents, simple random sampling was used for teachers and students.

There were 156 respondents, 11 (three English, four mathematics, and four science) teachers, and 145 students (100 Mat-I National High School and 45 Lubilan National School), enrolled in SY. 2023-2024 involved in the study. The survey questionnaire was adapted from a study by Ravitz and Richmond (2014).

Two survey questionnaires were used in this study: the survey questionnaire for teachers and students. The distribution and retrieval of survey instruments were conducted by the school. The data analysis process incorporated statistical techniques, including the computation of percentages, means, and standard deviations, as well as the execution of an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Prior to conducting the study, the researchers obtained necessary approvals by submitting formal requests to the DepEd Naawan District/DepEd Misamis Oriental and Division Office, along with all study participants. Furthermore, the parents of students taking part in the research were required to provide consent forms.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of teachers' perceptions of student engagement in collaborative skills highlights their significant commitment to integrating collaborative practices into classroom activities. Teachers report a high frequency of engaging students in activities that require collaboration, with the statements "Create joint products using contributions from each student" and "Present their group work to the class, teacher, or others" signifying the highest mean scores of 4.27 with an SD of 0.65 and 0.79 respectively. These scores indicate that such activities occur almost daily, underscoring the importance placed on students working together to produce shared outputs and present their collaborative efforts, which enhances teamwork and communication skills. In contrast, the activities "Work with other students to set goals and create a plan for their team," "Work as a team to incorporate feedback on group tasks or products," and "Give feedback to peers or assess other students' work" have the lowest mean scores of 4.09. This means that these practices were carried out 1-3 to times per week. The lower frequency may be due to the time required for goal-setting, incorporating feedback, and peer assessment, which are more complex and time-consuming tasks. The average overall mean score for collaborative activities was 4.17 (SD=0.78), 1-3 times per week. This shows that teachers regularly incorporate collaborative tasks into their teaching, although they particularly emphasize daily activities, such as joint product creation and presentations.

In evaluating the extent to which teachers agree with statements about their efforts in developing and accessing collaboration skills, the highest mean score of 4.20 (SD=0.63) is on the statement, "I have tried to develop students' collaboration skills." This assertion largely indicates their proactive efforts to improve students' teamwork skills and underscores their commitment to creating an environment that promotes collaborative learning. The statement "I have been able to assess students' collaboration skills effectively" had the lowest mean score of 3.64 (SD=0.67), which indicates agreement. This indicates that, while teachers agree, they assess the skills and are less confident in the effectiveness of these assessments. This suggests the challenges in comprehensively evaluating collaboration skills. The average mean score of 3.92 (SD=0.62) for the extent of agreement indicates that teachers generally agree to a great extent with statements about their efforts to develop and access collaboration skills. This high level of agreement shows satisfaction with the focus on collaboration but also points to potential areas for improvement in assessment practices. The overall mean score of 4.09 (SD=0.76) reflected a high level of engagement in promoting collaborative skills within the classroom. Teachers perceived themselves as highly involved in supporting collaborative activities, demonstrating a strong commitment to incorporating these practices into their teaching. This high overall mean reinforces the central role of collaboration in the instructional approach, highlighting a significant investment in fostering teamwork and collective learning among students.

Analysis of students' perceptions of collaborative skills revealed a moderate level of engagement with collaborative activities and perceptions of their development and assessment. The highest mean score of 3.43 is for "Give feedback to peers or assess other students' work," indicating that this activity occurs 1-3 times weekly. This indicates that students frequently

engage in peer feedback and assessment, which is a critical component of collaborative learning. Conversely, the lowest mean score is 3.24 for "Present their group work to the class, teacher, or others," indicating that such presentations are less frequent, occurring only 1-3 times per month. This lower frequency might indicate fewer opportunities for students to showcase their collaborative work, which could impact their communication and presentation skill development. The average mean score of 3.32 signifies that the overall students' engagement in collaborative activities is approximately 1-3 times per month. This signifies that, while collaborative activities are incorporated into the classroom, they are not as frequently emphasized as other types of engagement, potentially limiting opportunities for students to fully develop their collaborative skills. In the extent of agreement statements presented above, the highest mean score of 3.38 is on "I have tried to develop students' collaboration skills," reflecting a moderate agreement among students that their teachers make efforts to enhance collaborative skills. This indicates that students recognize their teachers' attempts to foster these skills. On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 2.98 is for "I have been able to effectively assess students' collaboration skills," fostering that the students feel teachers are less effective in assessing these skills. This lower score highlights a potential gap in the effectiveness of collaborative assessment practices. The average mean score for the extent of agreement was 3.18, indicating that students generally perceived their teachers' efforts and effectiveness in developing and accessing collaboration skills as moderate. This result suggests that there is some recognition of the teachers' efforts. There is also room for improvement in both the frequency of collaborative activities and effectiveness of their assessments. Moreover, the overall mean score of 3.27 reflects a moderate level of engagement in collaborative skills. This suggests that, while collaborative activities are present in the classroom, they may not be as prominently integrated or frequently practiced as other skills. The results indicate a need to increase both the frequency and effectiveness of collaborative activities and assessments to enhance students' collaborative skills and overall engagement in collaborative learning.

Furthermore, the survey analysis of the relationship between perceived teachers' teaching practices and students' perceptions of the teaching practices utilized by their teachers revealed a significant relationship between Collaborative Skills, with an F-value of 0.780 and a p-value of 0.013*. This finding indicates a notable link between how teachers perceive collaborative teaching practices and how they perceive them. A positive F-value suggests that a higher perception of collaborative teaching practices by teachers is associated with a more positive perception of these practices by students. Overall, the significant finding in Collaborative Skills highlights that teachers' self-perception can impact students' views in specific areas. This impact was not observed uniformly across all the teaching practices. The deeper learning approach, as described by William and Flora Hewlett Foundation (2010), focuses on several crucial educational goals. These encompass ensuring that students master fundamental academic disciplines, improving their ability to think critically and tackle complex problems, fostering teamwork skills, enhancing their capacity to communicate effectively, and cultivating techniques for independent learning. This initiative underscores the significance of students working together to enhance their educational experience.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study concluded that there is an association between teachers' perceptions and students' views on 21st century collaborative skills. It is recommended that this study be conducted in other schools with more respondents from other disciplines as well.

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